

Table 1. Remya (Mo 10) yields in Kerala, India.

	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Remya	Check variety ^b
RRS, Moncompu (field trials)	5.1	4.5
Multilocation trials 1983-84 wet season (5 locations)	6.8	5.4
All India Coordinated trials BPHRVT, 1984 dry season (11 locations)	4.9	3.3
BPHRVT, 1985 dry season (8 locations)	4.6	3.2
Farm trials 1988-89, 2 seasons (7 locations)	5.0	4.2

^a BPHRVT = Brown Planthopper Resistant Variety Trial.
^b Jaya for research station and multilocation trials, MR1523 for BPHRVT 1984, IET7575 for BPHRVT 1985, and Pavizham for farm trial.

Table 2. Remya reaction^a to pests and diseases at RRS, Moncompu, India.

Variety	Sheath blight	Sheath rot	Blast	Brown spot		Gall midge	BPH
				Leaf	Grain		
Remya	1.4	3.0	1.0	1.0	1.2	3.0	2.3
TNI	2.8	3.2	5.0	1.2	4.4	5.0	9.0

^a Standard evaluation system for rice scale of 0-9.

kernels and long bold grains which are qualities preferred by Keralites. It is semitall (100-110 cm).

In field and multilocation trials in 1983-84, it outyielded the check variety Jaya (Table 1). In All India Coordinated yield trials it ranked second out of 54 entries in 1984; in 1985, it ranked 7th out

of 50 entries. In farm trials during 1988-89, it outyielded the check variety in seven locations. Reactions to different pests and diseases are presented in Table 2.

Remya is recommended for all three seasons in Kerala. □

RCPL 1-1C, a cold-tolerant rice for high-altitude areas of Meghalaya, India

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Suboptimal temperature at reproductive phase, neck blast, and sheath rot are the major constraints to increasing rice production in high-altitude areas of NEH in India. Many exotic and indigenous lines from the National Cold Tolerance Nursery and the International

Table 1. Yield of RCPL 1-1C in Upper Shillong, India, 1985-90.

Cultivar	Grain yield (t/ha)					
	1985	1986 ^a	1987	1988	1989	1990
RCPL 1-1C	2.3	1.6	3.6	4.2	2.8	3.1
Khonorullo	1.9	1.3	2.9	3.3	2.1	2.5
Increase over check (%)	22	25	24	28	25	16

^aSevere rat damage (>50%).

Table 2. Yield of RCPL 1-1C in 2 farmers' fields in Meghalaya.

Variety	Grain yield (t/ha)	
	Mylliem (1700 m)	Sohiong (1650 m)
RCPL 1-1C	2.9	2.3
Khonorullo	1.7	2.0

Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery were evaluated at various growth stages. Most of them either exhibited poor spikelet fertility or did not set seed at all. Even the well-known cold-tolerant cultivars Stejaree 45, Barkat, Eiko, K39, K332, and CH1039 exhibited high spikelet sterility (>80%). Local cultivars, however, possess cold tolerance and have low spikelet sterility (<30%).

ICAR has developed a new line, RCPL 1-1C, at the experimental farm of Upper Shillong (1,850 mean sea level [msl], 25°32'N, 91°51'E), where average minimum and maximum temperatures are 11 and 19 °C at seedling stage, 15 and 20 °C at tillering and panicle initiation, and 9 and 18 °C at ripening. These temperatures are suboptimum for rice growth. Soil of the experimental area is loam with pH 5-4, 5.5% organic C, 11.8% clay, 46.3 ppm available P, and CEC 24.5 meq.

RCPL 1-1C, derived from Pusa 331 Khonorullo, is a cold-tolerant, high-

yielding indica rice. It matures in 165 d at high altitude (>1,300 msl), has moderate tillering (5-6) and semidwarf stature (90-95 cm), and is tolerant of low temperature (15-20°C) and short daylength (2-2.5 h sunlight/d) at the reproductive phase. It is also moderately tolerant of cold at the vegetative phase.

Kernels are medium slender and red. It has 1,000-grain weight of 22-23 g, and moderate resistance to blast and sheath rot. Yields range from 3 to 3.5 t/ha. Its spikelet sterility is very low (<20%) at optimum transplanting time (1st week of June) but becomes higher (40-50%) with later transplanting (up to last week of June).

In on-farm trials during 1985-90, mean yield was 2.3-4.2 t grain/ha, showing an advantage of 16-28% over Khonorullo, a local cold-tolerant cultivar (Table 1). It also did well in farmers' fields in adaptive trials in Meghalaya (Table 2). □

Space limitations prevent IRRN from publishing solely yield and yield component data from fertilizer field trials that are not conducted for at least two cropping seasons or at two differing sites. Publication of work in a single season or at one site is limited to manuscripts that provide either a) data and analysis beyond yield and yield components (e.g., floodwater parameters, microbial populations, soil mineral N dynamics, organic acid concentrations, or mineralization rates for organic N sources), or b) novel ways of interpreting yield and yield component data across seasons and sites.